

TM shift of M4K Pharma compounds with Alk5, Alk2 and RIPK2

Two compound plates used: K115 and K116. Both plates contain compounds from M4K Pharma and other related collaborators as well as K02288 as a positive control.

Make up protein solution to 2uM protein in 10mM Hepes, 50mM HEPES pH7.5

Add 1:1000 dilution of Sypro orange to 2.2ml of protein solution

Pipette 0.5ul of compound into the bottom of a 96 well PCR plate.

Pipette 19.5ul of protein into the wells.

Seal with optically active plate seals.

Spin down for 1 minute.

Run a thermal scan on an RT-PCR machine cycling from 20°C to 95°C over the course of 24 minutes.

Analyse results using excel and graph pad prism to integrate lines to find the midpoint and thus the Tm shift. DMSO only and Water controls embedded in the plate used to calculate reference cells from which to base the Tm shift from.

All results run in duplicate, however the second run of Alk2 plate K115 did not work due to machine malfunction.

Alk5 K115 1

Alk5 K115 2

Alk5 K116 (run twice in same plate)

Alk2 K115 (only 1 run due to second machine still not working despite replacement computer being set up)

Alk2 K116 (duplication in plate)

RIPK2 K115 1

RIPK2 K115 2

RIPK2 K116 (duplicated in plate)

